

MEYER'S 2-METHYL-4:6-DIPHENYLPYRIDINE : DETERMINATION OF THE STRUCTURE IN VIEW OF GASTALDI'S OBJECTIONS

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The controversy regarding the constitution of Meyer's pyridines obtained from dinitriles and arylidene-acetophenones has now been solved. Gastaldi's contention about the inaccuracy of the structure of one of Meyer's pyridines as 2-methyl-4:6-diphenylpyridine is proved to be true by two other independent syntheses of the pyridine, in each case the product agreeing with Gastaldi's compound. Meyer's product is shown to be an azafluorenone formed as a by-product by a secondary reaction, the main product being the normal Gastaldi's pyridine, obviously missed by Meyer due to its greater solubility in common solvents.

A method for the synthesis of pyridines from dinitriles was devised by V. Meyer (Meyer and Irmischer, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1908, 78, 497). The dinitrile is condensed with an arylidene-acetophenone in the presence of sodium ethoxide :

Gastaldi has thrown considerable doubt on the constitution of these products as he prepared 2-methyl-4:6-diphenylpyridine (III) (m.p. 73°) from the corresponding pyrylium salt (IV) and found it to be different from Meyer's pyridine (m.p. 156°) obtained from (I ; R=Me, Ar=Ph) by hydrolysis to (II) followed by decarboxylation (*Gazzetta*, 1922, 52, 169).

(II)

(III)

(IV)

(V)

In an earlier communication by one of us, it has been shown that the structure of Meyer's compounds as a class is not incorrect and so far as the particular member, e.g. 2-methyl-4:6-diphenylpyridine is concerned, Gastaldi's¹ contention is probably correct (Palit, this *Journal*, 1950, 27, 71).

Having established the correctness of Meyer's method, that for Gastaldi was therefore taken up. The correctness of constitution (IV) for Gastaldi's pyrylium salt received support from the work of Le Fèvre and Pearson, who synthesised the salt from benzoylacetone and acetophenone in the presence of ferric chloride and hydrochloric acid (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 1197). A convincing synthesis has now been

achieved by preparing the same salt from 2-methyl-6-phenyl- γ -pyrone (V) and phenylmagnesium bromide and treating the resulting compound with ferric chloride and hydrochloric acid.

These experiments have proved conclusively that both the above routes lead to the same pyridine of unquestionable structure, and if there is any difference in (III), obtained by the two methods, the explanation must be sought in the particular compound itself. An unambiguous synthesis of (III) was therefore undertaken. For this purpose, 2-hydroxy-4:6-diphenylpyridine (VI) (Basu, this *Journal*, 1930, 7, 490) was converted into the chloropyridine (VII), but attempts to replace the halogen atom by a methyl group through the malonyl derivative proved unsuccessful (cf. Königs and Fulde, *Ber.*, 1927, 60, 2106). The catalytic reduction of (VII) with Raney nickel furnished 2:4-diphenylpyridine (VIII), but attempts to add lithiummethyl to the azomethine linkage of this compound were also abortive (cf. Zeigler and Zeiser, *Ber.*, 1930, 63, 1847). Finally, ethyl 2-aminocrotonate was condensed with benzylidene ethylbenzoyl-acetate in the presence of diethylamine to give the dihydropyridine (IX), which was oxidised with nitrous fumes, hydrolysed with alcoholic potash and then distilled with lime, when (III) (m.p. 73°) was exclusively obtained.

It was abundantly clear that there must be something unusual in Meyer's mode of obtaining (III) and to examine this method more critically, Meyer's experiment was repeated with due care when it was noticed that the carboxypyridine (II) underwent decarboxylation smoothly, when heated above its melting point, and the product was identical with Gastaldi's pyridine as shown by mixed m.p. and comparison of ultraviolet absorption spectrum (Fig. 1). Meyer's method of decarboxylation by soda lime, however, gave a mixture, the main product being identical with Gastaldi's pyridine. The other product, obtained in poor yield, agreed with Meyer's compound of m.p. 156°. It is the latter which crystallises more readily from solvents such as light petroleum or benzene and the main product remains in solution which is probably the cause why Meyer had missed it. This yellow product analysed as $C_{10}H_{13}ON$ (Meyer gives no analysis for carbon and hydrogen) and was ketonic in character. The formation of this ketone from the acid (II) by loss of a molecule of water suggested it

to be an azafluorenone (XI) which was confirmed by a ring-closure in the acid by concentrated sulphuric acid at 100° (cf. Mills *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 2365) or through the corresponding acid chloride by Friedel-Crafts reaction (cf. Borsche and Hahn, *Annalen*, 1939, 537, 219). It is remarkable that the carboxy group of the acid (II) which

is so easily knocked off by mere heating above its m.p., should give the azafluorenone even in presence of soda lime.

Fig. 1

Absorption spectra of 2-methyl-4:6-diphenylpyridine.

A. From Meyer's method. B. Gastaldi's compound.

Reduction of (XI) by hydrazine hydrate at 200°-210° gave a quantitative yield of the azafluorene (XII) (cf. Borsche and Sinn, *Annalen*, 1937, 532, 146). The dicarboxy acid (X) on double cyclisation through the acid chloride gave 2:3:4:5-dibenzoylene-6-methylpyridine (XIII). The preparation of this diketone by an independent route has been recently described (cf. Petrow, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 2137).

EXPERIMENTAL

2-Methyl-4:6-diphenylpyrylium Ferrichloride (IV).—To a cooled solution of phenylmagnesium bromide from bromobenzene (2.5 g.) and magnesium (0.5 g.) in ether (40 c.c.) was added a solution of 2-methyl-6-phenyl- γ -pyrone (V) (2.7 g., Ruhemann, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, 93, 433). The yellowish white precipitate that appeared turned dark very soon and then the mixture was refluxed on the water-bath for 10 minutes. The complex was then decomposed with ice and hydrochloric acid. The aqueous layer was separated, treated with a solution of concentrated hydrochloric acid and ferric chloride, and the yellowish precipitate of the pyrylium salt (1.5 g.) crystallised from a

mixture of acetic anhydride and acetic acid. Compound (IV) was obtained in long yellow needles, m.p. 172-73°, undepressed on admixture with an authentic specimen prepared according to Gastaldi (*loc. cit.*). (Found: Cl, 31.6. $C_{18}H_{16}OCl_2Fe$ requires Cl, 31.9 per cent). The salt on treatment with ammonia gave (III), m.p. and mixed m.p., 73°.

2-Chloro-4:6-diphenylpyridine (VII).—A mixture of 2-hydroxy-4:6-diphenylpyridine (VI, 4.0 g.) and phosphorus oxychloride (15.0 g.) was treated with phosphorus pentachloride (15.0 g.). The mixture was heated on an oil-bath at 165°-170° for 6 hours, decomposed with ice and extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was washed with sodium hydroxide (6%), dried with anhydrous potassium carbonate and distilled. The distillate (2.1 g.) solidified quickly (b.p. 170°-175° / 0.24 mm.) and crystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 60°-80°) in colorless prisms, m.p. 64-65°. (Found: C, 76.4; H, 4.6; N, 5.3. $C_{17}H_{12}NCl$ requires C, 76.8; H, 4.5; N, 5.3 per cent).

Diphenylpyridine (VIII).—A solution of the above chloropyridine (VII, 1.0 g.) in alcoholic sodium ethoxide (sodium, 0.8 g. and dry alcohol, 50 c.c.) was hydrogenated at atmospheric pressure in the presence of Raney nickel (2 c.c., sediment). In 45 minutes the absorption of hydrogen was complete. The mixture was filtered, alcohol removed in a current of steam, the residue extracted with ether, dried (sodium sulphate) and distilled. The compound (VIII) (0.77 g.) was obtained at 160°-163°/0.2 mm. On cooling a solution of the distillate in petroleum ether with a sludge of dry ice in alcohol, the pyridine was obtained in prisms, m.p. 37-39°. On keeping the stable modification, m.p. 69° was obtained (Gastaldi, m.p. 69°). (Found: C, 88.4; H, 5.8; N, 5.6. $C_{17}H_{13}N$ requires C, 88.3; H, 5.6; N, 6.1 per cent).

The *acid sulphate* separated from dilute sulphuric acid (20%) in colorless long needles, m.p. 250-52° with slight browning (Gastaldi, m.p. 245°). (Found: C, 62.1; H, 4.5; N, 4.1. $C_{17}H_{13}N.H_2SO_4$ requires C, 62.0; H, 4.6; N, 4.3 per cent).

The *picrate* crystallised from alcohol in light yellow plates, m.p. 187-88° (Gastaldi, *Gazzetta*, 1922, 52, 305, gives m.p. 187°). (Found: C, 60.3; H, 3.7; N, 11.6. $C_{17}H_{13}N.C_6H_3O_7N_3$ requires C, 60.0; H, 3.5; N, 12.1 per cent).

The *picrolonate* was obtained from amyl alcohol in fine yellow needles, m.p. 183-84° (decomp.). (Found: C, 65.4; H, 4.4; N, 14.1. $C_{17}H_{13}N.C_{10}H_8O_2N_4$ requires C, 65.4; H, 4.2; N, 14.1 per cent).

2:4-Diphenyl-3:5-dicarboethoxy-6-methyl-dihydropyridine (IX).—A solution of benzylidene ethylbenzoylacetate (20.0 g.) and ethyl 2-aminocrotonate (20.0 g., used in excess) in absolute alcohol (20 c.c.) was treated with diethylamine (2.0 c.c.). The solution maintained at 50° turned yellow and the crystals of (IX) appeared in the course of 3 hours. After allowing to stand for 3 days at 50°-60°, the crystals (16.0 g.) were collected and were obtained from alcohol in colorless needles, m.p. 190-92°. A slow evolution of gas occurs at a few degrees above the m.p.; this is probably due to the removal of a carboethoxy group followed by the aromatisation of the pyridine ring (cf. Guareschi and Grande, *Chem. Zentr.*, 1899, II, 440). (Found: N, 3.5. $C_{24}H_{25}O_4N$ requires N, 3.6 per cent).

2:4-Diphenyl-3:5-dicarboxy-6-methylpyridine (X).—Nitrous fumes were passed into a cold suspension of (IX, 10.0 g.) in alcohol (25 c.c.). The solid gradually passed into solution which was poured on ice, extracted with ether and washed with sodium

carbonate. The ethereal solution was dried (potassium carbonate) and gave on evaporation 2:4-diphenyl-3:5-dicarboethoxy-6-methylpyridine as a viscous liquid which was hydrolysed with alcoholic potash (50 c.c., 30%) by boiling under reflux for 5 hours. The potassium salt separated in an hour. It was collected (8.2 g) and washed successively with a small amount of dry alcohol and dry ether. The salt is very hygroscopic. The corresponding acid (X) (3.2 g.) was obtained on treating the salt (4.0 g.) with an equivalent amount of hydrochloric acid. It crystallised from aqueous alcohol (charcoal) in colorless prismatic needles, m.p. 287-88° (decomp.). The crystals contain water of crystallisation which is easily removed by heating in vacuum at 120° for 1 hour. (Found: N, 4.4; equiv., 165.5. $C_{26}H_{15}O_4N$ requires N, 4.2 per cent. Equiv., 166.5).

2-Methyl-4:6-diphenylpyridine (III).—An intimate mixture of the above potassium salt (3.5 g.) and calcium hydroxide (7.0 g.) was heated strongly in a horizontal tube closed at one end. A thick oil, which distilled slowly, solidified readily (1.4 g.) and crystallised from petroleum ether in colorless prisms, m.p. 69-70°. On purification by chromatography in petroleum ether solution on alumina (Brockmann), (III) was obtained pure, m.p. 73°, undepressed on admixture with Gastaldi's pyridine. (Found: N, 5.7. $C_{18}H_{15}N$ requires N, 5.7 per cent).

Decarboxylation of Meyer's Acid (II). *Method (a)*.—The acid was heated on a metal bath the temperature of which was gradually raised from 260° to 290°. The evolution of carbon dioxide was complete in a few minutes. The residue on distillation gave a quantitative yield of (III), which on purification by chromatography, was obtained in prisms, m.p. 73°, undepressed on admixture with Gastaldi's pyridine. (Found: C, 88.1; H, 5.9; N, 5.6. $C_{18}H_{15}N$ requires C, 83.1; H, 6.1; N, 5.7 per cent).

The *picrate* crystallised from butanol in yellow plates, m.p. 213° (Dilthey, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1916, 94, 53, gives m.p. 212-13°). (Found: C, 61.0; H, 3.5; N, 12.0. $C_{18}H_{15}N \cdot C_6H_3O_7N_3$ requires C, 60.8; H, 3.8; N, 11.8 per cent).

The *picrolonate* crystallised from alcohol in yellow needles, m.p. 187-88° (decomp.). (Found: C, 66.0; H, 4.4; N, 13.9. $C_{18}H_{15}N \cdot C_{10}H_8O_4N_4$ requires C, 66.0; H, 4.4; N, 13.8 per cent).

Method (b) (Meyer's method).—An intimate mixture of the acid (1.0 g.) and soda lime (4.0 g.) was heated carefully with a smoky flame in vacuum and the distillate was collected on a cold finger. This was dissolved in petroleum ether, filtered and concentrated. The solution deposited yellow needles (ca. 50 mg.), m.p. 148-52° which were purified by chromatography in petroleum solution on an alumina column. The yellow band (green fluorescence in ultraviolet light) was eluted by a mixture of petroleum ether and benzene (3:2). The material crystallised from light petroleum in yellow leaflets, m.p. 156° (Meyer, m.p. 156°). The compound is feebly basic and dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid with a deep yellow solution. (Found: C, 83.9; H, 5.0; N, 5.3. $C_{16}H_{11}ON$ requires C, 84.1; H, 4.8; N, 5.2 per cent). The compound was ketonic and furnished an oxime, m.p. 290° (decomp.) which was not depressed on admixture with the oxime of (XI) mentioned below. The petroleum mother-liquor on concentration gave a gummy mass (0.5 g.) which slowly crystallised. This was identified as (III) by m.p. and mixed m.p.

1-Methyl-3-phenyl-2-azafluorenone (XI). *Method (a)*.—The compound (II) (1.5 g.) was converted into the acid chloride by refluxing with thionyl chloride (8 c.c.) for 4

hours. The crystalline acid chloride was dissolved in warm freshly distilled nitrobenzene (30 c.c.) and then cooled and treated with anhydrous aluminium chloride (1.7 g.) in small portions. The deep yellow coloured mixture was maintained at 50°-60° for 1½ hours. The complex was then decomposed with ice and hydrochloric acid and the nitrobenzene removed in a current of steam. The residue was treated with sodium acetate (10 g.) and the sulphur-yellow precipitate (1.3 g.) was collected and crystallised from a mixture of benzene and light petroleum. The compound (XI) was obtained in light yellow flat needles, m.p. 155-56°, undepressed on admixture with Meyer's so-called "2-methyl-4:6-diphenylpyridine". The compound dissolved in concentrated sulphuric acid giving a deep yellow solution. (Found: N, 5.2. $C_{11}H_{12}ON$ requires N, 5.2 per cent).

Method (b).—The acid (II, 0.2 g.) was dissolved in concentrated sulphuric acid (1 c.c.) and heated at 100° on the water-bath for 8 hours. On pouring the orange-red solution into water, a yellow crystalline precipitate at once appeared. The whole was made alkaline to litmus and the precipitate collected (0.18 g.) and crystallised from petrolbenzene mixture in flat yellow needles, m.p. 156°.

Oxime.—A solution of the ketone (0.5 g.) in pyridine (25 c.c.) was heated on the steam-bath with hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.5 g.) for 1½ hours and then left over night at the room temperature. The oxime, precipitated by addition of water, crystallised from butanol in fine, long, colorless needles (0.3 g.), m.p. 291-92° (decomp., darkening at 285°). (Found: N, 9.7. $C_{11}H_{14}ON_2$ requires N, 9.8 per cent).

1-Methyl-3-phenyl-2-azafluorene (XII).—The above ketone (XI, 0.3 g.) was treated with hydrazine hydrate (1 c.c., 100%) and heated in a sealed tube at 200°-210° for 24 hours. The azafluorene was obtained as a colorless solid (0.27 g.), crystallising from methyl alcohol in light colorless needles, m.p. 104-105°. (Found: N, 5.5. $C_{19}H_{13}N$ requires N, 5.4 per cent). The *picrate* was obtained from methyl alcohol in yellow needles, m.p. 209-11° (decomp.). (Found: N, 11.4. $C_{19}H_{13}N.C_6H_5O_7N_3$ requires N, 11.5 per cent).

2:3:4:5-Dibenzoylene-6-methylpyridine (XIII).—The acid (X, 1.4 g.) was converted into the acid chloride by heating with thionyl chloride (20 c.c.) for 2 hours. A cold solution of the acid chloride in nitrobenzene (15 c.c.) was treated with anhydrous aluminium chloride (2.4 g.), the whole allowed to attain the room temperature and then warmed at 60°-65° for 11 hours. The mixture was then decomposed with ice and hydrochloric acid and nitrobenzene removed by steam distillation. A dark brown gum was left which was boiled with a mixture of ethyl alcohol (130 c.c.) and *n*-butyl alcohol (100 c.c.). The yellow crystalline precipitate (0.45 g.) after treatment with alkali was crystallised from pyridine in yellow needles. m. p. 260-62°. Petrow (*loc. cit.*) gives m. p. 263° (corr.). (Found: N, 4.7. $C_{20}H_{11}O_2N$ requires N, 4.7 per cent). The compound gives a deep yellow coloration with concentrated sulphuric acid. The *dioxime* crystallised from pyridine in nearly colorless needles, which shrinks at 320° and decomposes at higher temperature. (Found: N, 12.6. $C_{20}H_{13}O_2N_2$ requires N, 12.8 per cent).

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